

Customer Satisfaction with Institutional Services Among Fourth-Year Business Administration Students at North Negros College, Cadiz City

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of customer satisfaction of fourth-year BSBA students towards the services offered by North Negros College during the Academic Year 2024–2025 and to serve as a basis for the formulation of a development program to improve institutional services. Regarding the respondents' profiles, the majority were older female students. Regarding satisfaction levels, Student Personnel Services, Library Services, Finance Services, and Campus Facilities were rated as moderately satisfied, while Guidance Services was rated highly satisfied. When all areas were combined, respondents' overall customer satisfaction was moderate. When respondents were grouped by age, there was no significant difference in customer satisfaction across all service areas. However, when grouped by sex, significant difference was found in Student Personnel Services, Finance Services, Campus Facilities, and across all areas. No significant difference was observed in the areas of Guidance Services and Library Services. The findings revealed that age does not affect students' level of customer satisfaction, whereas sex does in selected service areas. Guidance Services emerged as the institution's strongest area, while Library Services, Finance Services, and Campus Facilities were identified as areas needing improvement. Based on the study's results, it is recommended that North Negros College enhance library resources and internet connectivity, strengthen scholarship and financial assistance programs, improve campus facilities, particularly recreational areas, and adopt gender-sensitive approaches to service delivery. The formulation and implementation of a development program are therefore necessary to enhance the quality of service and increase student satisfaction.

Keywords: BSBA Students, Customer Satisfaction, Student Services

How to Cite:

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INTRODUCTION

Organizations rely on repeat customers to sustain growth and success, and this principle also applies to academic institutions. Customer loyalty is strongly influenced by satisfaction with the quality of services provided, as incentives alone are not enough to maintain long-term engagement. Recent studies emphasize that meeting customer needs and expectations enhances satisfaction and encourages continued patronage, particularly in service-oriented sectors (Kotler, Keller, & Chernev, 2021; Slack & Singh, 2020). In the context of education, institutions strive to deliver high-quality services and positive experiences to foster student loyalty and strengthen their reputation.

This study focuses on evaluating the quality of services provided by the institution as a means of improving competitiveness and attracting and retaining students and faculty. Internal assessments play a crucial role in enhancing campus experiences, particularly in addressing student retention and graduation rates. Student satisfaction with academic and support services has been identified as a key factor in demonstrating the value of education to both students and their families and in improving institutional outcomes (Ali et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2022). Ultimately, improving service quality contributes to student satisfaction, institutional effectiveness, and long-term success.

It is in this context that the researchers have been motivated to conduct this study for the North Negros College graduating students particularly from the College of Business Administration.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the customer satisfaction with institutional services among fourth-year Business Administration Students at North Negros College in the Academic Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following: 1) the level of satisfaction of the respondents in terms of student personnel services, guidance services, library services, finance services, and campus facilities; 2) the significant differences in the level of customer satisfaction when the respondents are group according to the variables; 3) the significant differences in the level of satisfaction when the respondents are group according to the aforementioned areas.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Student satisfaction has become a vital indicator of institutional effectiveness in higher education, particularly in service-oriented settings. Research by Slack and Singh (2020) emphasizes that service quality including responsiveness, reliability, and assurance directly impacts students' perceptions of educational institutions. Satisfaction extends beyond classroom instruction to encompass administrative, support, and campus-related services, collectively shaping the overall student experience.

Student support services, such as guidance, counseling, and student personnel programs, have grown in importance due to their influence on student well-being and retention. Singh and Jasial (2021) found that trust and perceived service quality strongly predict satisfaction, with accessible and reliable guidance fostering confidence and engagement. Similarly, mental health and stress management services, particularly highlighted after the COVID-19 pandemic, enhance students' coping mechanisms and contribute to higher satisfaction levels (Aristovnik et al., 2020).

Library and digital services are critical to academic satisfaction, especially with increased reliance on online resources. Studies by Tan, Muskat, and Zehrer (2022) and Johnson, Veletsianos, and Seaman (2021) indicate that access to updated learning materials, e-books, databases, and stable internet connectivity significantly affects students' perceptions of service quality. Inadequate resources or technological deficiencies contribute to dissatisfaction, demonstrating the essential role of library and digital infrastructure in modern education.

Financial services and institutional transparency are also central to student satisfaction. Efficient financial processes, scholarship accessibility, and clear communication regarding fees positively influence perceptions of fairness and trust, while slow or opaque procedures decrease satisfaction (Dugenio-Nadela et al., 2023; Cazan & Truța, 2021). These findings highlight the importance of financial support systems in addressing students' academic and personal needs and reducing stress.

Campus facilities, including safety, cleanliness, recreational spaces, and modern infrastructure, significantly shape students' daily experiences. Ali et al. (2021) and Temizer and Turkeyilmaz (2020) note that well-maintained, secure, and student-friendly environments enhance motivation, emotional well-being, and perceived institutional value. Conversely, inadequate facilities can diminish satisfaction despite strong academic quality, underscoring the role of the physical campus in holistic student experiences.

Demographic factors, particularly sex and age, influence how students perceive institutional services. Research by Kotler, Keller, and Chernev (2021) and Gupta and Kaul (2023) indicates that gender differences affect satisfaction with areas such as campus

safety, financial services, and support facilities. These findings support the adoption of gender-sensitive policies to ensure equitable and inclusive service delivery, reinforcing the importance of tailoring services to diverse student needs.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

The descriptive research design was used to determine the level of customer satisfaction of 4th year BSBA Students in North Negros College, Cadiz City for SY 2024-2025. According to Sarantakos (2013) descriptive research is research that seeks to describe and interpret the characteristics, behaviors, or patterns of a particular group or phenomenon. It involves the systematic collection and analysis of data to generate a descriptive account.

Study Respondents

The study respondents were (no. of respondents) who are BSBA 4th year students within the locale of the study. The researcher had given the self-made questionnaire to every classroom. Random sampling was used in the conduct of the study. It is a statistical technique used to select a subset of individuals from a larger population, where each individual has an equal chance of being chosen. This method is crucial in ensuring that the sample is representative of the population, thereby allowing for the generalization of results from the sample to the population as a whole (Lindsey, C. 2017).

Instruments

This study utilized a survey questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument, defined as a written tool consisting of a series of questions designed to gather information from respondents (Babbie, 2016). A self-made questionnaire was administered to fourth-year students, allowing them to complete it independently to minimize interviewer bias (Bodine, 2022). The questionnaire gone through validation of experts and run reliability test to ensure that the questionnaire is highly reliable. The collected data were then coded into numerical values using a coding manual to assess levels of skills and degrees of difficulty. Data processing and analysis were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel, and statistical tables were constructed based on the research problems outlined in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher sought permission from the college Dean to undertake the study. Accordingly, a letter request was sent to the school administrator. Upon approval, the researcher schedules the questionnaire's administration on a mutually convenient schedule for the respondents and the researcher. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the target respondents. An orientation was done to present the objectives of the study and how to answer the survey questionnaire. The researcher assures the respondents that all data gathered in this study are treated with the utmost confidentiality. Upon retrieval of the survey questionnaire, the data gathered was sent to the statistician for tabulation, application of the appropriate statistical tools in every problem, analysis, and presentation of the data in a tabular manner.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 Descriptive analytical scheme and mean was used to determine the level of customer satisfaction in 4th year BSBA students in North Negros College for SY 2024-2025 in the following areas: student personnel services, guidance services, library services, finance services and campus services.

Objective No. 2 Descriptive analytical scheme and mean was used to determine the level of customer satisfaction in 4th year BSBA students in North Negros College for SY 2024-2025 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 3 Comparative analytical scheme and Mann Whitney U Test was used to determine whether or not significant differences exists in the level of customer satisfaction in 4th year BSBA students in North Negros College for SY 2024-2025 when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations in research are a set of principles that guide your research designs and practices. Scientists and researchers must always adhere to a certain code of conduct when collecting data from people, (P. Bhandari, 2022) Voluntary participation, Informed consent, confidentiality and plagiarism will be strictly considered. Participants of the study will not be forced or pressured; they can withdraw any time without giving any reason to withdraw. Participants of the study will be thoroughly informed about the purpose and nature of the study including the benefits and risks and consequences. Participants of the study will be assured of the confidentiality of all information relevant to the personal information or any form of identifying information relating to their person.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the Area of Student Personnel Services

Student Personnel Services		Mean	Interpretation
1.	Quality and variety of food option on Campus	3.11	Moderately Satisfied
2.	Student leadership opportunities	3.29	Moderately Satisfied
3.	Ample opportunities to join clubs.	3.44	Moderately Satisfied
4.	Health services easily accessible	3.34	Moderately Satisfied
5.	Clinic Equipment is readily available	3.23	Moderately Satisfied
Mean		3.28	Moderately Satisfied

The level of satisfaction of the 3rd year BSBA students in the area of Student Personnel Services is reflected in Table 1. Ample opportunities to join clubs got the highest mean score of 3.44 and the quality and variety of food option on campus has a mean score of 3.11 which got the lowest mean, both were interpreted as moderately satisfied.

These implies that students had some opportunities to join campus organizations or clubs, however their desire to join clubs was only moderately satisfied which means, they had some opportunities to join clubs but perhaps not or many as they shaped for or perhaps the opportunities that were available did not meet their expectations. On the item about the quality and variety of food option, it implies that students may not feel encourage to explore different cuisines or food options due to limited variety, students may experience repetition with the available food options which potentially leading to dissatisfaction.

Table 2

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the Area of Guidance Services

Guidance Services		Mean	Interpretation
1.	Availability of counselling service	4.11	Highly Satisfied
2.	Sufficient resources for stress management	3.42	Moderately Satisfied
3.	Availability of Mental health facilities	3.33	Moderately Satisfied
4.	Institution promotes of healthy work life	3.35	Moderately Satisfied
5.	Availability of career services	3.35	Moderately Satisfied
Mean		3.51	Highly Satisfied

Availability of counselling services in this area got the highest total mean score of 4.11 interpreted as highly satisfied and the item on the availability of mental health facilities got the lowest mean score of 3.33 which is interpreted as moderately satisfied. The overall mean in the area of Guidance Services got the total mean score of 3.51 which is interpreted as highly satisfied. This implies that students feel that the guidance services are readily available, accessible and provide effective support, students have trust and confidence in the guidance services, receiving them as a valuable resource.

In the item on the availability of mental health facilities, the low rating implies that student's demand for mental health support are not being met, potentially leading to increased stress, anxiety and other mental concerns, moreover this concerns can

significantly impact academic performance, leading to decreased grades, absenteeism and decreased motivation. This implies that students feel that the instructional materials and online resources are sufficient for this academic needs but lack variety, depth or relevance, students may also encountered difficulties accessing or utilizing certain resources, or found them outdated, incomplete & irrelevant.

Table 3

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the Area of Library Services

Library Services	Mean	Interpretation
1. Printed Materials	2.92	Moderately Satisfied
2. Audio-Visual Materials	2.81	Moderately Satisfied
3. Instructional Materials	3.17	Moderately Satisfied
4. Online resources like e-Books & journals available	3.17	Moderately Satisfied
5. Internet connection	2.42	Dissatisfied
Mean	2.90	Moderately Satisfied

There were two items in this area which got the highest mean score of 3.17 which are both interpreted as moderately satisfied. The item Instructional Materials and online resources like e-books & journals available. The item internet connection got the lowest mean score of 2.42 interpreted as dissatisfied. Moreover, internet connection in the area of library services got the lowest mean score which implies that poor internet connection can hinder users' availability to access online data bases, e-books, and other digital resources, which are essential for research and learning, libraries with poor internet connection maybe at a disadvantage compared to other libraries or study spaces that offer faster and more reliable connections.

Table 4

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the Area of Finance Services

Finance Services	Mean	Interpretation
1. Financial aid services	2.84	Moderately Satisfied
2. Accessible payment system	2.84	Moderately Satisfied
3. Student assistance	2.87	Moderately Satisfied
4. Scholarship program	2.75	Moderately Satisfied
5. Cashiers are fast in facilitating payments	2.99	Moderately Satisfied
Mean	2.86	Moderately Satisfied

The level of satisfaction of the 3rd year BSBA students in the area of Finance Services is reflected in table 4. Cashiers are fast in facilitating payment got the highest mean score of 2.99 which is interpreted as moderately satisfied in contrary the item scholarship program got the mean score of 2.75 interpreted as moderately satisfied. These implies that moderate speed in facilitating payment might lead to moderate customer satisfaction customers may not be overly impressed, but they won't be dissatisfied either. Moderate speed could indicate that cashiers are balancing efficiency with accuracy they are not rushing through transactions, which could lead to errors, but they are not also showing down the process. On the other hand, the item scholarship program of the institution got the lowest mean score which implies that the scholarship may not be meeting its intended goals or providing sufficient support to student furthermore the institution may not be providing adequate academic financial assistants to scholarship recipient, leading to higher drop outs.

Table 5

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the Area of Campus Facilities

Campus Facilities	Mean	Interpretation
Cleanliness and Maintenance of Campus buildings	3.09	Moderately Satisfied
Have a quiet place to study on campus	2.86	Moderately Satisfied
Campus signage is clear in finding way/s.	3.11	Moderately Satisfied
Recreational area like gym is beneficial	2.53	Moderately Satisfied
Safety served well in the campus.	3.15	Moderately Satisfied

Mean 2.95 Moderately Satisfied

As shown in table 5, item number 5 which states that safety served well in the campus got the highest mean score of 3.15 interpreted a moderately satisfied. The lowest mean score of 2.53 which is interpreted as moderately satisfied was score in item number 4 which state the recreational area like gym is beneficial. The total mean score of this area of Campus Facilities is 2.95 interpreted as moderately satisfied. This implies that students feel that the safety services are sufficient but not outstanding. Students may still have concerns about specific safety issues, such as lighting, emergency response or campus security. Moderate satisfaction with safety services may affect students’ over-all experience and sense of well-being. The lowest mean of 2.53 was scored in item number 4 which states that recreational area like gym is beneficial. This implies that the area is not meeting their expectation which least to dissatisfaction, it may lack modern equipment, sufficient space or variety in facilities which lead to customer dissatisfaction. The overall mean in the area of Campus facilities scored 2.95 which is interpreted as moderately satisfied. This implies that campus facilities meet basic needs but lack of exceptional features leading to the result of moderate satisfaction. Facilities may require upgrades, or renovations to enhance the overall student experience.

Table 6

Level of Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students When All Areas Are Taken Altogether

All Areas	Mean	Interpretation
1. Student Personnel Services	3.28	Moderately Satisfied
2. Guidance Services	3.51	Highly Satisfied
3. Library Services	2.90	Moderately Satisfied
4. Finance Services	2.86	Moderately Satisfied
5. Campus Facilities	2.95	Moderately Satisfied
Mean	3.10	Moderately Satisfied

Table 6 shows no.2 for Guidance Services got the total mean score of 3.51 interpreted as highly satisfied, while item no.1 in the area of library services has a total mean score of 3.28 interpreted as moderately satisfied. The overall mean in this area when taken altogether is 3.10 interpreted as moderately satisfied. It implies that students feel that the guidance services are effective in supporting their academic and personal needs. Guidance counselors are seen as trusted advisors providing valuable guidance support. The lowest mean was in the area of library services. This implies that students feel that the library is not meeting their information needs, they perceived the library’s resources such as books, journals or data bases, as inadequate and outdated. Inadequate library services can hinder students’ ability to conduct research, complete assignment and learn effectively.

Table 7

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the area of Student Personnel Services When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	106.58	3443.000	0.459	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	114.99				
Gender	Male	54	130.07	3749.000	0.032		Significant
	Female	172	108.30				

The difference in the level of satisfaction in the area of student personnel services when grouped and compared to variables is reflected in table 7. When respondents were group and compared according to age there was no significant difference found, but variable on gender between male and female there was a significant difference found.

This implies that male and female students may have different needs and expectations when it comes to student personnel services (SPS) leading to varying level of satisfaction, the significant difference may indicate that one gender has less access to SPS resources, such as academic advising or support groups.

Table 8

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the area of Guidance Services When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	111.43	3637.000	0.824	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	113.95				
Gender	Male	54	124.23	4064.500	0.165		Not Significant
	Female	172	110.13				

The difference in the level of satisfaction in the area of guidance services when grouped and compared according to variables is reflected in table 8. When the respondents were group and compared according to the aforementioned variables there was no significant difference found. It means that students across different age groups and genders reported similar levels of satisfaction with guidance services indicating a consistent experience furthermore the absence of significant difference suggest that guidance services are accessible and effective for all students, regardless of age or gender.

Table 9

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the area of Library Services When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	106.00	3420.000	0.423	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	115.11				
Gender	Male	54	128.31	3844.000	0.056		Not Significant
	Female	172	108.85				

The difference level of satisfaction in the area of library services when grouped and compared according to variables is reflected in table 9. When respondents were grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables there was no significant difference found. It means that students of different age groups and gender either male or female reported similar levels of satisfaction with library services indicating equitable access. Library services seem to be supportive of both male and female student’s needs.

Table 10

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the area of Finance Services When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	113.89	3704.500	0.967	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	113.42				
Gender	Male	54	135.34	3464.500	0.005		Significant
	Female	172	106.64				

The difference level of satisfaction in the area of financial services when grouped and compared according to variables is reflected in table 10. When respondents were group and compared according to age there was no significant difference found, but variable on gender between male and female there was a significant difference found. This implies that male and female students may have different needs, perceptions, or expectations regarding financial services. The difference may indicate that one gender—likely female students, based on the lower mean rank—may experience less favorable access to or effectiveness of finance-related support, such as payment processing, financial aid assistance, or information dissemination.

Table 11

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students in the area of Campus Facilities When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	114.30	3688.000	0.932	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	113.33				
Gender	Male	54	139.70	3229.000	0.001		Significant
	Female	172	105.27				

The difference level of satisfaction in the area of campus facilities when grouped and compared according to variables is reflected in table 11. When respondents were group and compared according to age there was no significant difference found, but variable on gender between male and female there was a significant difference found. This implies that male and female students may have different needs, expectations, or experiences regarding campus facilities. The difference with male students showing higher mean ranks may suggest that female students have less favorable access to or satisfaction with certain aspects of the facilities—such as cleanliness, comfort, safety, or availability of gender-responsive spaces.

Table 12

Difference in the Satisfaction of the 4th Year BSBA Students When Areas Are Taken Altogether and When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	40	109.95	3578.000	0.705	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	186	114.26				
Gender	Male	54	133.98	3538.000	0.008		Significant
	Female	172	107.07				

The difference level of satisfaction in the areas taken altogether when grouped and compared according to variables is reflected in table 12. When respondents were group and compared according to age there was no significant difference found, but variable on gender between male and female there was a significant difference found. This implies that male and female students may have different overall experiences, needs, or expectations regarding the institution's various services, which affects their general satisfaction. It shows the importance of evaluating institutional services through a gender-sensitive, ensuring that programs and resources are inclusive, accessible, and responsive to the unique concerns of all students.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the majority of respondents were older students and predominantly female. Overall, the graduating BSBA students of North Negros College reported being moderately satisfied with institutional services. Among service areas, Guidance Services received the highest satisfaction ratings, particularly for counseling availability, while Library Services, especially internet connectivity, received the lowest. Student Personnel Services, Finance Services, and Campus Facilities were rated moderately satisfied, with specific strengths in club opportunities, cashier services, and campus safety, and weaknesses in food variety, scholarship programs, and recreational facilities. Satisfaction levels did not significantly differ by age, but sex influenced perceptions in Student Personnel Services, Finance Services, Campus Facilities, and overall satisfaction. These findings indicate that while basic needs are met, improvements are needed in Library Services, Finance, and Campus Facilities to enhance overall student satisfaction and address gender-based differences in service experiences.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the institution is recommended to enhance Student Personnel Services by offering more diverse and affordable food options and expanding student organization opportunities. Guidance Services should strengthen mental health facilities and stress management programs, while Library Services should prioritize improving internet connectivity and updating resources to support academic research. Finance Services require improvements in scholarship programs and financial aid to ensure equitable support, and Campus Facilities should upgrade recreational areas, study spaces, and safety features to

enhance the overall student experience. Additionally, adopting gender-sensitive policies is advised to address the differing needs and expectations of male and female students, ensuring inclusive and equitable service delivery.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to the conduct, authorship, and publication of this research. All procedures and interpretations were performed independently, and no financial, professional, or personal relationships influenced the results of this study.

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